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RESEARCH ARTICLE

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INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP CONSTELLATION FOR THE 21ST CENTURY CHANGES IN SCHOOLING THROUGH MOBILE TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the implications of new constellations for instructional leadership arising from the growing adoption of the 21st-century reform movement as considered by policymakers in the country and around the world. The dramatic and radical changes proposed by school mission and visions, systems, and pedagogy as set by educators, policymakers, and business makers are deemed essential to ensure a vibrant and sustainable global community where school principals are required to step out from behind their managerial desks and enter to a facilitative and contributive role in guiding and directing instructional changes in schools across the country through diverse modes of instruction delivery. The key objective of this article is to promote educational leadership and change through teachers and principals who can impact student engagement in the 21st century through mobile technology. In the methodology section, equitable allocation of resources was emphasized to promote digital literacy, instructional progress was measured for fostering a culture of collaboration around instructional development, and teachers were encouraged to collaborate on their specialized learning for instructional improvement. Instructors and leaders as a result could learn and practice the necessary technical, leadership, and managerial skills to be participants in a vibrant democracy while ensuring that members work as a group to meet the learning needs of each student.

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INTRODUCTION

An overview of the dramatic, radical, and even revolutionary change was sought after as workplaces and communities have changed globally. Our community involves global politics, global economies, and global health and environment issues and this requires all of us to have a sharp departure from the way we teach and learn in our schools and focus on learner's capacity to learn, create, and to work collaboratively together on real-life topics. The main objective of this article was to promote educational leadership and change through teachers and principals who can guide and impact student learning in the 21st century through mobile technology. Instructional leadership includes intentional effort at all levels of an education system to guide, direct, or support teachers as they seek to increase their repertoire of skills, gain professional knowledge, and ultimately improve their student's success by being concerned with the full range of activities being carried out by various educators that offer teachers ideas, assistance, and moral support specifically directed at instruction and that motivates and even compel teachers to try to improve. Instructional leadership is inherently distributed across different levels in the school system where we intentionally broaden the focus from the work done by the individuals to the collective work that groups of individuals and teams do. Works of literature point out that those advocating for a radical revision of education for

the future predicate, this change in the dramatically different context where the people that have the knowledge and the skills to negotiate a constant change in this situation would be able to succeed. Pine [1] suggested that we are now transitioning into an 'Experience' economy with a much more human-centric approach. It was these influences that were causing business and Government leaders to invade education. The scope and vision of this article rest on the forces that integrate core curriculum subjects to lenses of 21st-century themes and redesign them using the latest mode of instruction delivery using mobile technology to lighten up and focus on big ideas like critical thinking and problem-solving, creativity, and risk-taking, collaboration, team-work and leadership, cross-cultural understanding, oral and written communication, computing and ICT literacy, career, building work ethic and learning self-reliance that transcends subject matter domains by developing suitable assessment protocols while focusing on their real, current and future needs.

METHODOLOGY

Digital Literacy Improvement through Equitable Allocation of Resources: The significance of this conceptual work lies in how leaders of learning institutes could plan to achieve an equitable allocation of resources for learning improvement using different modes of instruction delivery. Educational resources include people,

time, and money whether it comes to funding, quality teaching, instructional time, or academic rigor. The best way to achieve an equitable allocation of resources for digital literacy improvement was to conduct a meaningful resource allocation review where clear guidance to schoolteachers was preset. Dedicate adequate time and money to the monitoring process and publish clear protocols to measure the progress of strategic implementation to eliminate inequalities. Selection and implementation of strategies to address identified inequities, e.g., ensuring that underserved students are not being taught by novice teachers or implementing a team-teaching model pairing bilingual teachers with content teachers to better address the needs of English learners. Communicating about strategic resource (re) allocation decisions with teachers, parents, students, and other stakeholders can help in coming to a standpoint before resource allocation. The 'Every Student Succeeds Act' requires school resource allocation review where schools identified for improvement based on low performance for individual groups of students must identify and address resource inequities within their school. Therefore, a plan to review inequities in school funding as deemed necessary to be developed to use the resources supported by all funding sources — federal, state, and local, including both general funds and funds dedicated to school improvement activities for the improvements in • Teaching quality • School leadership quality • Academic rigor • Instructional time and attention • Early learning and early interventions • Whole child approaches • Diverse and inclusive schools • Family academic engagement. Sufficient learning resources are required to be allocated to meet the learning needs of each student and school and students with additional needs have additional resources relative to their peer needs to be established. Students of color and students from low-income families continue to face substantial systemic barriers today and need additional support with digital learning resources to overcome those barriers. School leaders need to work smart with the help of digital technologies and mobile equipment to help schools and students deal with the daily challenges of poverty and racism with the additional technical support needed to succeed.

Roadmap to Instructional Leadership through Collective Efficacy for Instructional Progress: A rigorous review of the literature suggests that the roadmap from instructional leadership to teachers' instructional progress was one way to comprehend the key linkages among forms of enactive experiences that promote collective efficacy beliefs in the school system. By fostering a culture of collaboration around instructional development, leaders can sustain school improvement in districts in a manner that optimistically influences teachers' collective efficacy principles and thus promotes student achievement both at the school level and district level. There exist theoretical relationships among principal leadership, teacher collaboration for instructional improvement, collective efficacy beliefs, and student achievement. A strong direct predictor of collective efficacy beliefs was the outcome that the degree of teacher collaboration likely depends on the strength of instructional leadership branding a school or school district, which is significant when judging teacher collaboration for instructional improvement. Explicitly, asking teachers to respond regarding the magnitude to which their principals and superintendents were knowledgeable about effective evaluation, and instructional practices and provided conceptual advice to teachers regarding these practices; set high metrics for teaching and learning; were conscious of classroom practices; made systematic and frequent classroom visits; and were directly involved in aiding teachers to improve the overall learning and instructional practices.

The assertion was that school improvement involves strong instructional leadership and persistent work among teachers on teaching and learning. The healthier the sense of collective effectiveness characterizing the schools, the superior their levels of student achievement, even after limiting school and student background characteristics and prior levels of student achievement. Prior research significantly supports that principals should set high benchmarks for teaching and learning; be well-informed about and seek teacher participation concerning instruction, curriculum, and assessment [5-8]; spend time in classrooms so that principals are

informed of instructional habits in their schools [10]; and empower teachers to work in collaboration by creating formal structures aimed at assisting teachers' collaborative endeavors to enhance instruction and learning [11]. Several research findings depict the extent to which teachers collaborate to enhance instruction was strongly projected by principals' instructional leadership. Findings reveal that apparent collective efficacy was a substantial positive predictor of disparities among schools in student achievement. Indeed, the strength of this linkage suggests that schools and districts in which principals were testified by teachers to regularly monitor instruction and to deliver comparatively strong instructional support blended with the latest technology were the ones most likely demonstrated by elevated levels of collective work among teachers to enhance instruction delivery. The psychometric analysis conducted among teachers can provide robust support for the validity and reliability of scores to gauge teacher collaboration as an impact on instructional policy, collaboration frequency, and the degree of formalization of teacher collaboration. Studies ascertain that principal leadership is an essential criterion to build teacher collaboration and thus to work toward improved student outcomes. The strong interrelationship between principal leadership and teacher collaboration was detected to be consistent with several research results that implied the significance of strong instructional leadership to teachers' collaborative effort and school improvement [9].

Instructional Enhancement to Improve Teaching and Learning: Both instructional leadership and teacher collaboration for instructional improvement using the latest platform of learning delivery are crucial indirect predictors of variations among schools and school districts in student academic achievement. Strategies to ensure frequent, formal, and focused collaboration through instructional improvement emphasize accruing benefits from formally designed time for teachers to collaborate on their specialized learning in mobile technology for instructional improvement. Such effort is essential in the future, to establish common agreements of good student work and to diagnose and respond to student misunderstandings. Furthermore, one of the most effective forms of rigorous teacher collaboration that principals could endorse is teachers' observations of other teachers' classrooms to form a common perception of good teaching practice. While much more investigation is still needed to comprehend the relative advantages of within and cross-school or district observation and under what circumstances, it seems that these findings signal a clear necessity for principals to endorse sustained connections around instructional enhancement to improve teaching and learning. Identically, while research establishes the direct connection between collective efficacy and student achievement [2-4], the style in which school district leaders and teachers perform together to improve instruction and collective efficacy beliefs demands more attention. As suggested by past research findings, strong instructional leadership was essential even to establish technological structures like mobile learning in support of student engagement. Leaders would need to offer time for teachers to collaborate frequently as well as to support a formal framework for teachers' collaborative work. Additionally, various modes of instruction delivery would help in supporting teachers' collective effort in school and school district progress efforts related to selecting and gauging instructional materials and approaches, as well as professional development efforts, which would improve teachers' collective beliefs in their abilities to teach all students productively.

Results and Implications: A vital ethical role for an educational leader in the professional spectrum is to clarify the behavioral guidelines for every member of the organization because all these relations can be reflected in school activities, teacher training workshops, board meetings, and school policies. Playing an ethical role as an educational leader in every context or situation helps a leader in making more objective and suitable decisions. The change brought about through instructional leadership practices enabled the school leaders to easily adapt to technological solutions like 'Zoom', 'Twitter', Microsoft 'team', Google 'Hangouts' and 'Whatsapp' messenger via mobile devices while facing learning challenges thrown by the school infrastructure, which would have

otherwise disrupted normal career growth. Instructional leadership practices allow school leaders to learn and practice the necessary technical, leadership, and managerial skills to be participants in a vibrant democracy while ensuring that members' work style as a group and then arrive at a decision on analyzing the group dynamics to minimize grievances from all stakeholders and ensure group members work in collaboration. Instructional leaders could incorporate learning strategies such as Universal Design for Learning (UDL) wherein differentiation was offered to meet the needs of all students, lessons were structured with multiple entry points, and students were offered multiple ways to demonstrate understanding to ensure academic enrichment and enhancement in learning outcome through technological intervention. Instructional reforms could be brought about by the team of instructors to change the traditional measures of school achievement through innovative means whether supported by the board or not to ensure pedagogical transformation towards better cultural responsiveness. Several learning aids were thought to be redesigned to enrich students' experience in learning and enhance learning perception. Instructional staff and school leaders' actions were more intentional and geared towards the contextual needs of the student population, and parents, by taking proactive stances in tailoring learning programs to fit the student needs while ensuring member identity, group emphasis, and community focus to lead to empowerment and continuity among students. Besides, it was detected that within multiple contexts, the dynamic interactions and relations among contexts also affect the leadership practices and behavior to shape various contexts in routine work and to focus on a common organizational mission and vision.

CONCLUSION

The approaches outlined in this article recognize school leaders as catalytic change agents and utilize active visionary experts at the school level to incorporate the digital delivery of instructions through mobile technology. Principals as school leaders are a leading force in reducing the amount of time and effort spent on managing school affairs involved in guiding and directing the learning of teachers and working collaboratively with the teachers to enable them to become facilitators of student learning through systematic changes along with bringing changes in the current operation of learning and teaching process by accessing the gap between current and 21st-century teaching practices coupled with ongoing engagement and observation of learning across the school. In conclusion, leaders and principals constantly learn about the changes in pedagogical and curricular design intrinsic to 21st-century models and become active and engaged leaders to promote the 'Every Student Succeeds Act'.

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